

Bioactive glass (BG) particle shape affects the mechanical and biological properties of PLA/BG scaffolds for bone regeneration

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ABSTRACT

The impact of the addition of flame-spheroidized bioactive glass microspheres (BGMs) on the properties of poly (lactic acid) (PLA) composite filaments and scaffolds for bone regeneration is evaluated. Cube-shaped scaffolds were fabricated using fused deposition modeling. Scanning electron microscopy confirmed a uniform BGM distribution within the polymer matrix. PLA/BGM filaments demonstrated superior tensile strength to those containing irregularly-shaped particles. Scaffolds produced from PLA/BGM filaments exhibited enhanced compressive strength, achieving higher stress values at 30% strain. In-vitro studies with MG-63 cells revealed the highest cell viability of PLA/BGM scaffolds after seven days of incubation. These findings highlight the potential of BGMs to enhance mechanical and biological performance of PLA-based scaffolds, advancing their application in bone regeneration.

1. Introduction

Bioactive glasses (BGs) have been widely used in bone tissue engineering (BTE) applications since their discovery more than 50 years ago due to their bioactivity, biocompatibility, and osteoconductivity [1]. Among others, S53P4, a BG composition for medical use in certain bone grafting applications, exhibits superior network stability along with inherent antibacterial, bioactive, osteogenic, and anti-inflammatory properties [2,3]. BG particles are often of irregular shape, especially in applications requiring a large amount of feedstock. The combination of irregularly shaped BGs with a polymer matrix like poly(lactic acid) (PLA) for BTE scaffolding is well-documented [4,5]. For instance, Distler et al. [5] fabricated composite scaffolds using PLA filaments containing irregularly-shaped 45S5 BGs. In another study, Schätzlein et al. [6] used irregularly-shaped S53P4 BGs to prepare PLA filaments for scaffold fabrication in BTE. Bioactive glass microspheres (BGMs) are spherically engineered versions of irregularly-shaped particles (ISPs). Until now, limited attention has been paid to the use of BGMs in three-dimensional (3D) printing applications [7]. However, such microspheres have the potential to significantly enhance various properties of 3D-printed

scaffolds, including compactness, mechanical stability, and high solid loading, making them an excellent material choice for BTE applications [8].

This study examines the influence of BGMs shape on the mechanical and biological properties of composite scaffolds fabricated using a solvent-free method, with PLA as the matrix. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first investigation of the fabrication of PLA filaments incorporating BGMs for 3D printing (fused deposition modeling).

2. Materials and Methods

Bioactive glass powders were fabricated by melt-quenching, crushing, and sieving through a 40 μm sieve. The nominal compositions (wt. %) of the BGs used in this study denoted as S53P4 (base glass) and S53P4_10B are given in Table S1. The S53P4_10B BG was utilized as the precursor for microsphere fabrication. The precursor was fed into an oxygen-methane torch using a vacuum powder feeder, operating at a controlled rate of 2.2 g/min, with oxygen utilized as a carrier gas for powder feeding. The resulting microspheres (denoted as S53P4_10B_M) were sieved < 40 μm . Composite filaments were fabricated, with

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Fig. 1. SEM cross-sectional images of (a,b,d) PLA/S53P4_10B_M and (c) PLA/S53P4 filaments subjected to tensile testing.

preparation details provided in the [supplementary data](#). The shape and distribution of BG particles within the PLA matrix were examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Filament cross-sections were prepared by cryogenic fracturing. Tensile strength was measured using a universal testing machine (Frank, Germany; $n = 10$) following DIN 53455, at a deformation rate of 10 mm/s with a 5 kN load cell.

The prepared PLA/BG filaments were used to print samples using an FDM printer (CR-10 SE, Creality, China). Compression testing of cube-shaped ($xyz = 10$ mm) scaffolds was performed as described in the [supplementary data](#). Disc-shaped scaffolds (6 mm diameter, 0.5 mm height) were immersed in simulated body fluid (SBF) following the Kokubo method [9] to assess bioactivity (see [supplementary data](#) for details). Cytotoxicity of scaffolds ($xy = 10$ mm, $z = 2$ mm) was assessed using MG-63 human osteoblast-like cells (Sigma Aldrich, Germany), as outlined in the [supplementary data](#). All biological experiments were performed in triplicate. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilised with significance levels set at $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, and $***p < 0.001$ to statistically evaluate the results.

3. Results and discussion

XRD analysis confirmed the amorphous nature of the prepared glasses ([Fig. S1](#)), while ICP-OES analysis verified that the compositions of glasses were consistent with their nominal values ([Table S1](#)). Following the flame synthesis process, the reduction in B_2O_3 (from 9.8 to 5.1 wt.%) and Na_2O (from 20.2 to 17 wt.%) contents was attributed to volatilization during flame spheroidization at high temperatures (1850 °C).

[Fig. 1](#) shows SEM images of the cross-section of PLA/S53P4_10B_M and PLA/S53P4. [Fig. 1a](#) confirms that the filaments containing BGMs were successfully produced with high thickness accuracy. [Fig. 1b](#) and [1c](#) show the homogeneous distribution of both ISPs and BGMs in the matrix. [Fig. 1d](#) shows the position of a single microsphere within the polymer matrix.

[Table S2](#) presents the results of the prepared filaments' tensile strength and elastic modulus. The neat PLA filament exhibited the highest tensile strength of 58 ± 2 MPa among all samples, as also

illustrated in [Fig. 2a](#). The group containing BGMs demonstrated the highest tensile strength (53 ± 1 MPa) and elastic modulus (1.1 ± 0.1 GPa) among the filaments containing BGs. Two mechanisms likely contribute to the enhancement: i) the spherical shape of the BGMs reduces their specific surface area compared to ISPs of similar size, this lower surface area decreases interfacial interactions between the particles and the PLA matrix, improving matrix compactness and load distribution. ii) The spherical particles are more uniformly encapsulated by PLA ([Fig. 2b](#)). In contrast, ISPs tend to create larger voids or gaps within the composite, as indicated by the red arrows in [Fig. 2c](#). The presence of these voids impairs the mechanical properties by preventing complete infiltration and adhesion of PLA, thereby reducing overall strength.

[Fig. 2d](#) presents the compressive strength values for cube-shaped scaffolds, while [Table S3](#) provides a numerical summary of these values. The PLA/S53P4 scaffolds exhibited the lowest elastic modulus (0.17 ± 0.02 GPa). The PLA/BGMs scaffolds demonstrated higher stress resistance at 30 % strain (21 ± 1 MPa) than the other samples, even surpassing the compressive strength of neat PLA (19 ± 1 MPa). These values meet the recommended mechanical properties for human trabecular bone (compressive strength: 2–12 MPa; elastic modulus: 0.1–5 GPa) [10,11]. The uniaxial compressive stress applied to the top layer was effectively transmitted to subsequent layers, maintaining structural stability and preventing immediate distortion ([Fig. 2e](#)). With increasing stress, the columns between layers began to collapse in the z-direction, significantly reducing porosity. In the PLA/S53P4 scaffolds, brittle fracture occurred ([Fig. 2f](#), red arrows), leaving open pores that indicate insufficient stress transmission along the z-direction, which resulted in structural distortion. This observation supports the second explanation of the tensile test results. The scaffolds containing S53P4_10B BG exhibited greater structural integrity under 30 % strain, as seen in PLA/S53P4_10B_M scaffolds. Some indications of distortion were observed, including the persistence of open pores and noticeable lateral bending (blue arrows), suggesting that the ISPs within the scaffold contributed to localised stress resistance, similar to PLA/S53P4 scaffolds. As shown in [Fig. 2h](#), increased stress led to the collapse of the initial layers (highlighted by the dashed blue rectangle) rather than the complete scaffold collapse observed in PLA-only scaffolds. This suggests

Fig. 2. (a) Tensile test results of all prepared filaments; (b,c) SEM cross-sectional images of cryogenically fractured filaments; (d) compression test results of all 3D-printed scaffolds; (e-h) optical images (side view) of scaffolds after compression testing.

that BGMs help distribute stress more effectively, reducing catastrophic failure.

Fig. 3a, 3b, and 3c demonstrate bioactivity and cell viability results of the samples. All PLA/BG discs showed bioactivity expressed in terms of calcium-phosphate formation on their surfaces. Fig. 3a illustrates the typical cauliflower-like shape of calcium-phosphate rich phases on the surface of BGMs [12]. The FTIR results (Fig. 3b) show the bands related to phosphate and carbonate groups, supporting the SEM results. The WST-8 results of PLA/BG scaffolds seeded with MG-63 cells are shown in Fig. 3c. Compared to the control group (neat PLA), PLA/S53P4_10B scaffolds exhibited lower cell viability after seven days of incubation. This situation can be linked to either faster dissolution of boron, exceeding the acceptable therapeutic ion level in the media, or the rapid increase in local pH due to the dissolution [13,14]. PLA/S53P4_10B_M scaffolds showed higher cell viability than the control group after seven days of incubation.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the role of filler shape in improving the mechanical and biological performance of PLA/BG composites. PLA/S53P4_10B_M scaffolds showed superior cell viability and bioactivity, making them suitable candidates for BTE. SEM examination confirmed uniform dispersion of BGMs, enhancing the mechanical performance of both filaments and scaffolds. However, the stress and load propagation

mechanisms in these polymer-inorganic composites remain unclear. The findings emphasise the potential of BGMs to enhance polymer composites for advanced BTE applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ertugrul Varlik: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lucille Viviant:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Fatih Kurtuldu:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Qaisar Nawaz:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Si Chen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Jozef Kraxner:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Dušan Galusek:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Martin Michálek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Aldo R. Boccaccini:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 3. In-vitro bioactivity and cell viability results of the 3D-printed PLA/BG samples: (a) SEM image of a 3D-printed PLA/S53P4_10B_M disc immersed in SBF for 28 days, (b) FTIR results of all samples immersed in SBF for 7 and 28 days, and (c) cell viability results of MG-63 cells on PLA/BG scaffolds. Statistical significance is indicated as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2025.139383>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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